

Azatriterpenes. VI. Synthesis of 2-Eno[2,3-*g*]pyrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyrimidines of Pentacyclic Triterpenes

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Condensation of 3-aminopyrazole with 2-hydroxymethylene derivatives of methyl betulonate (1), lupenone (2) and methyl oleanonate (3) in absolute ethanol furnished their respective 2-eno[2,3-*g*]pyrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyrimidines (4, 5 and 6). They were characterised by elemental and spectral data.

RING-A fused heterocycles of triterpenoids were synthesised earlier in our laboratory¹⁻³ with a view to induce biological activity to biologically inert triterpenoids, as fusion of heterocyclic ring or incorporation of hetero atom into steroidal nucleus had modified their physiological activity⁴⁻⁷. Sykes and Bajwa synthesised a number of new steroidal heterocycles by the condensation of 2-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazole⁸, 4-amino-1,2,4-triazole⁹, 3-aminopyrazole¹⁰, 3-amino-1,2,4-triazole¹¹ etc. with various steroidal β -ketoaldehydes.

In the present investigation, 2-hydroxymethylene derivatives of methyl betulonate² (1), lupenone (2) and methyl oleanonate³ (3) were condensed with 3-aminopyrazole in absolute ethanol. Sykes and Bajwa observed the formation of angularly and linearly fused pyrazolopyrimidines (7, 8) in the condensation of 3-aminopyrazole with 2-hydroxymethylene derivatives of 3-oxo steroids¹⁰. The 5'-proton showed signal at δ 8.15 in the angularly fused product (7) whereas the 7'-proton showed a signal at δ 8.37 in the linearly fused product (8). In the present case, the nmr spectra of all the three 2-eno[2,3-*g*]pyrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyrimidines (4, 5 and 6) showed signal at δ 8.15 characteristic of 5'-H. This confirms the angularly fused nature of the products.

Experimental

The melting points were recorded using Bio-Chem melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. Nmr spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ on a EM-360 60 MHz spectrometer with TMS as the internal standard. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-

6

7

8

Elmer Infra Cord 237 spectrophotometer and uv spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer.

2-Hydroxymethylene-lup-20(29)-en-3-one (2): To lupenone (2 g) in dry benzene (25 ml) freshly distilled dimethyl formamide (5 ml), freshly distilled ethyl formate (5 ml) and sodium methoxide solution (25 ml) prepared from sodium (5 g) were added and refluxed for 8 h. The reaction mixture was cooled, acidified and extracted with ether. The ether extract furnished the 2-formyl derivative as colourless solid (1.5 g) crystallising from methanol as colourless needles (2), m.p. 180-82° (Found: C, 82.55; H, 10.60. $C_{31}H_{48}O_3$ requires: C, 82.30; H, 10.62%); δ 8.6 (1H, s, CHO); ν_{max} 3 150 cm^{-1} (chelated OH) and 1 680 cm^{-1} (CHO); λ_{max} (EtOH) 284 nm, underwent a bathochromic shift of 20 nm in base (EtOH-0.1 N NaOH).

A Typical experiment for the condensation of 3-aminopyrazole with β -keto aldehyde of pentacyclic triterpenes (1-3). Isolation of 2-eno[2,3-g]pyrazolo[1,5-a]pyrimidines (4-6): A solution of the triterpene β -keto aldehyde (800 mg) and 3-aminopyrazole (200 mg) in absolute ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed for 12 h. The mixture was evaporated to dryness *in vacuo*. The residue was adsorbed over neutral alumina (Acme) and eluted with petroleum ether (500 ml) and benzene (1.5 l). Petroleum ether eluate did not yield any residue. Benzene eluate yielded 2-eno[2,3-g]pyrazolo[1,5-a]pyrimidines

(500 mg) which were finally purified by crystallisation from $CHCl_3$ -MeOH as colourless needles. Methyl 2-eno[2,3-g]pyrazolo[1,5-a]pyrimidine-lup-20(29)-en-28-oate (4), m.p. 140-45° (Found: C, 77.02; H, 9.42; N, 7.98. $C_{33}H_{48}O_3N_3$ requires: C, 77.34; H, 9.02 and N, 7.73%); δ 6.60 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, 3'-H), 8.0 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, 2'-H), 8.15 (1H, s, 5'-H), 4.7 (2H, d, J 6.5 Hz, $C=CH_2$), 3.65 (3H, s, COOMe) and 0.9-2.5 (18H, 6 \times Me). 2-Eno-[2,3-g]pyrazolo[1,5-a]pyrimidine-lup-20(29)-ene (5): m.p. 225-30° (Found: C, 81.36; H, 10.02; N, 8.01. $C_{34}H_{48}N_3$ requires: C, 81.77; H, 9.82 and N, 8.41%); δ 6.60 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, 3'-H), 8.0 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, 2'-H), 8.15 (1H, s, 5'-H), 4.7 (2H, d, J 6.5 Hz, $C=CH_2$) and 0.9-2.5 (21H, 7 \times Me). Methyl 2-eno-[2,3-g]pyrazolo[1,5-a]pyrimidine olean-12-en-28-oate (6): m.p. 260-65° (Found: C, 77.62; H, 9.12; N, 7.88. $C_{33}H_{48}O_3N_3$ requires: C, 77.34; H, 9.02 and N, 7.73%); δ 6.60 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, 3'-H), 8.0 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, 2'-H), 8.15 (1H, s, 5'-H), 5.3 (1H, t, 12-H), 3.65 (3H, s, COOMe) and 0.9-2.5 (21H, 7 \times Me).

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